

Comparative Analysis between Somatotype and Fitness Status of Middle-Aged Female Adults in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study compared somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state, Nigeria. The research design for the study was the modified pretest, mid and post-test quasi experimental design using a cluster of female adults within a population of residents in the Noman's land area of Kano state. Samples were made up middle-aged female adults (N=44) who volunteered to take part in the eight (8)-week aerobic exercise training program. Instrument used for data collection included direct measurement of height and weight using the bathroom height and weight scale (Portspring model 005; made in England); and calibrated equipment for body composition variables (%BF, Waist and Hip circumferences and somatotype) at 0, 4, and 8 weeks of aerobic training following standard procedures. Simple percentages were used to describe changes during exercise training, while the One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test hypotheses which are deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level. Based on the findings, it was revealed that an 8-week aerobic exercise programme caused significant changes in body composition (weight, %BF, waist circumference), and slight but a non-significant change in somatotype of subjects. It was concluded that well-organized exercise training can modify body composition and somatotype status in females and yield positive dividends to health and well-being. Therefore, it is recommended that participants and other fitness enthusiasts should continue exercising regularly; and start if they have not done so, while they watch their food intake in order to maintain the desired somatotype level appropriate for optimum health benefits.

Keywords: Aerobic exercise, Body fat percent, Ponderal index, Somatotype

Introduction

Body typing is a commonly applied feature to describe people in different vocations and professions. It tells us that bodies come in different shapes and sizes, influenced by a person's frame and composition; and can be summarized as size and geometry of individuals (Tungdim, 2024). This physical size and shape of a person's body, is a genetic or biological material usually passed down or inherited from the progenitor; even though environment, lifestyle and level of fitness can affect and modify this inherited trait of such persons. Human body shape is a complex phenomenon with sophisticated details and functions. The general shape or figure of a person is defined mainly by the molding of skeletal structures, as well as the distribution of muscles and fat (Wikipedia, 2023). In the study of human performance, body typing is commonly referred to as somatotype. A somatotype is a quantitative overall appraisal of the present shape and composition of the human body (Richardson, 2022). In psychology, there is this discredited idea that human body shape and physique type are associated with personality traits, forming the basis of constitutional psychology; whereas this phenomenon comes in handy in law and criminal investigation in which crimes are not only traced but attributed to certain body shapes and sizes (Nickerson, 2023). Theoretically, the somatotype refers to a generalized set of body types, the skeletal frame and body composition that an individual is genetically endowed with (Langford & Norwood, 2023). Thus, all humans have specific body characteristics that can be traced to related lineage.

The somatotype theory also states that there is an association between an individual's body type and certain personality or behavioral traits. Biological criminology theories state that some individuals are predisposed to committing crimes due to their biological nature, such as genetics, brain neurology and physical appearance (Nickerson, 2023). This theory was deduced from a study of delinquent juvenile male college students following a decade-long study. Participants were ranked based on their body type and it was discovered that many juvenile males had a mesomorphic body type, whereas most college males had an ectomorphic body type; thereby attributing mesomorphs to criminal tendencies. Today, the three body types of endomorph, mesomorph and ectomorph were a theoretical extension of embryonic development from which an individual's body type is dependent on how many embryonic layers one has viz: the inner layer (endoderm), middle layer (mesoderm) and the outer layer (ectoderm) (Tungdim, 2024). All these layers describe the functional elements that form the body structure and consequently, the physique.

To classify a body type in any of the described component reflects the extent of attainment on the anthropometric scale based on the measured variables. These variables according to Amusa & Igbunugo (2013), include skinfold, body circumferences and diameters, height and body weight. The considerable interest today in using body composition analysis in sports and physical fitness programmes is related to setting a minimum for health and sports in order to ensure optimum health and fitness. The size and geometry of a person's body, Owolabi (2015) opined, may impose constraints upon his capacity for motor performance. He went further to say there are desirable body composition for motor performance and variation from sport to sport. This opinion is supported by somatotype studies which observed that people with relatively similar body types tend to consistently participate in selected sports (Novoa-Vignau, et al.; (2017). Thus, it can be implied that one may be capable of predicting performance success in ball games from physique and body composition factors.

The quality of the sports-specific performance attributes tends to vary according to the skill or the body composition status and the level of attainment of the performer being higher in the champion athlete and lower in the poor ones; and may be expected to vary among group ability levels (Owolabi, 2015). In other words, it is expected that significant differences will be found when fitness enthusiasts and national athletes are compared with their Olympic counter parts in terms of their somatotype and fitness characteristics due to their levels of training.

Of the several methods which appeal to exercise scientists in determining somatotype status of humans, the anthropometric technique which can be used in field assessment comes in handy; hence, it is easily applied while carrying out fitness assessment. Different body type, be it ectomorphic, mesomorphic and endomorphic, can influence an individual's response to aerobic fitness training (American Alliance of Health, Physical Education, Recreation and Dance [AAHPERD] 2015). For instance, the ectomorphs with a characteristic lean and thin physique presents the advantages of low body mass which may enhance running economy and endurance and has less body fat to lose, potentially making weight management easier. The mesomorphs, on the other hand, have muscular and athletic build which can enhance performance and their efficient muscle-to-fat ratio aids endurance in all kinds of athletic performance; while the endomorphs are curvy and soft and have generally stronger upper body, which when guided, can lose weight and improve on their cardiovascular health with training (Kim & Kim 2017).

The descriptions of positive sides of the three body types are not without their disadvantages as lower muscle mass may limit power output with the accompanying difficulty building muscle endurance in ectomorphs; higher muscle mass may increase risk of overtraining causing the mesomorphs to struggle with achieving flexibility; and endomorphs on the other hand, has higher body fat percentage that reduces endurance and increases their risk for cardiovascular disease (Meschino, 2020). Despite these negative aspects, all fitness components depend on body composition to the extent that an increase in lean body mass contributes to strength and power development while strength and power are related to muscle size. Thus, an increase in lean body mass enables the athlete to generate more force in a specific period of time (Westcott & Laing, 2006).

Recognizing that somatotype is just one factor influencing aerobic fitness, aside genetics, age, nutrition, lifestyle and overall physical performance; it has been proved that exercise training can cause positive response to excessive body fat accumulation (Baranauskas, 2024). Besides the great benefits, its evaluation offers a guideline for fitness and selection of exercise for sporting activities; and in adults, encourages the development of fitness capabilities; and positive health maintenance. It is in line with the above, this study carried out a comparative analysis of somatotype and fitness status among middle-aged female adults in Kano state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To compare changes in body weight of middle-aged female adults in Kano state following aerobic exercise training program in Kano state.

2. To analyse effects of modification in the body fat percent (%BF) on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state
3. To analyse effects of modification in waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of female adults in Kano state
4. To compare changes in the somatotype components of the middle-aged female adults following fitness training in Kano state.

Research Questions

1. Are there changes in body weight of middle-aged female adults following aerobic exercise training program in Kano state?
2. Are there effects of modifications in body fat percent (%BF) on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?
3. Are there effects of modifications in Waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?
4. Are there changes in somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following fitness training program in Kano state?

Hypotheses

1. **H₀₁:** Aerobic exercise training program will not cause significant changes on body weight of middle-aged female adults in Kano state
2. **H₀₂:** There are no significant effects of %BF modifications on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female in Kano State
3. **H₀₃:** There are no significant effects of modifications in waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state
4. **H₀₄:** There are no significant changes in the somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following training program in Kano state.

Methodology

To achieve the purpose of this study, the modified pre-test, mid and post-test quasi experimental design (Venkateswarlu, 2015) was employed with no manipulation of variable. This design was deemed appropriate because variable measurement at the commencement, during and at cessation of training could provide the results needed for the target population. The population comprised all middle-aged females (N=180) in Kano state who were neither sedentary nor very active except for their activities of daily living (ADL). Out of this population, a sample of forty-four (44) middle-aged female volunteers took part in the aerobic training programme based on factors of location, occupation and accessibility to the training center. Volunteers were administered with consent form which described the procedure of test administration. The fitness center used for aerobic training operated a flexible four (4) hour-daily programme from 4pm to 8pm on any three (3) alternate days from Monday to Friday following guidelines of the American College of Sports Medicine [ACSM], (2014). Trained research assistants were always available to administer a 30-45-minute aerobic exercise training to subjects in groups.

The instrument comprised calibrated equipment required for direct measurement on selected variables of interest (height, body weight, waist and hip circumferences, muscle girths, epicondylar diameters and skinfold thickness) (Adeyanju & Dikko, 2015) at 0wk, 4weeks and 8weeks of aerobic training, following standard procedures; using the following instruments:

1. The portable bathroom salter scale to measure height, body weight; non-elastic tape rule for measurement of waist and hip circumferences of subjects; and the Vernier caliper (ICI Inc, USA) was used to measure muscle girths, epicondylar diameters and skinfold thicknesses in selected sites to estimate %BF and somatotype of subjects. All data were collected at 0wk, 4weeks and 8weeks of aerobic training and recorded; however, subjects' height measurement was not repeated because it is believed no changes could occur (Olaniyi, 2009; Venkateswarlu, 2015).
2. While using the anthropometric formulae described by Heyward & Wagner, (2014) and Novoa-Vignau et al.; (2017), selected sites were measured and values obtained were fed into constants for endomorph; $-0.7182+0.1451(x)-0.00068(x^2)+0.000014(x^3)$ in which x is the sum of the triceps, subscapular, and supraspinale folds, multiplied by (70.18/height(cm); mesomorph = $(0.858 \times H) + (0.601 \times F) + (0.188 \times B) + 0.161 \times P - (0.131 \times E) + 4.5$ and the Parnell's 1990 method of ectomorph assessment derived from lean body weight formular $(LBW = (\sum 8D)^2 / 101 \times ht (m))$. All the data obtained were summarized and analyzed with descriptive statistics [Frequencies and percentages (%)] and inferential statistics [One way analysis of variance (ANOVA)] to determine if the aerobic exercise training

programme significant roles in modifying the somatotype and fitness status of subjects in the study. All hypotheses were deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level.

Presentation of Results

Data collected for this study are presented in line with the research questions and adequately described while the inferential statistics of one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses raised for the study. All hypotheses are deemed significant at 0.05 alpha level as shown below:

Research Question 1

Are there changes in height and body weight of middle-aged female adults following aerobic exercise training program in Kano state?

Table 1: Physical characteristics of height and weight of subjects in the training programme

Variable	Before (0wk0)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
a. Height (m)	1.68m	1.68m	1.68m	1.68m
b. Weight (kg)	74.5kg	74.2kg	72.7kg	0.3kg

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

Data on height (Table 1a) showed 1.68m as average height of subjects which remained unchanged, as expected, throughout the duration of the exercise. However, data collected on subjects' weight (Table 1b) (at 0 week = 74.5kg; 4 weeks = 74.2kg (diff. 0.3kg); and at the completion of training (at 8 weeks = 72.7kg) showed a cumulative 1.8kg (4.09%) difference which can be attributed to the aerobic training programme. This shows that adult height is not expected to be modified during an exercise training programme, whereas this cannot be said of weight which can be affected by exertion over a period of time. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was employed for analysis, the results of which are presented in Table 2.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: Aerobic exercise training will not cause significant changes on body weight of middle-aged female adults in Kano state

Table 2: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on weight changes

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
Weight	0.3kg	1.8kg (4.09%)	F=1.018	3.21	NS
			F=3.312*		Sig

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ *Significant

On Table 2 is the result of inferential statistics of One-way ANOVA employed to analyse data on weight values following exercise training. The result was not significant after 4 weeks ($F_{(2,44)}=1.018 < 0.05$); whereas significant difference was recorded after 8 weeks of aerobic training ($F_{(2,44)}=3.312 > 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted after 4weeks of training but rejected at the end of the training program. It can, therefore, be inferred that the longer the exercise training program takes, the more the gains that can be recorded in respect of weight loss.

Research Question 2

Are there effects of modifications in body fat percent (%BF) on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?

Table 3: Percent body fat (%BF) estimates of subjects in the study

Variable	Before (0wks)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
% BF	25.5%	24.8%	22.4%	0.7%

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

A glance at table 2 revealed records of body fat percent (%BF) which was estimated from the subject's height and weight values (W/ht^2) [Quetelet Index (QI)] from which the body mass index (BMI) was derived, and the corresponding %BF values read off a nomogram (Heyward, 2017). The estimated %BF values recorded at 0, 4 and 8 weeks were 25.5%; 24.8% and 22.4% respectively representing 0.7% and 3.1% reduction after 4 and 8weeks of training respectively following aerobic exercise

training. This result followed the trend reported in body weight in which bodily exertion has caused reductions in %BF from 25.5% to 22.4% following exercise training. This is an indication that the training programme probably resulted in the reduction in %BF. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was employed for analysis, the results are presented in Table 4.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₂: There are no significant effects of %BF modifications on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female in Kano State

Table 4: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on modifications in %BF

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
%BF	0.7%	3.1%	F=0.164	3.21	NS
			F=4.041*		Sig

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ *Significant

As presented in Table 4, %BF values analysed with One-way ANOVA, revealed no significant reduction ($F_{(2,44)} = 0.164 < 0.05$) after 4weeks whereas significant reduction was recorded after 8weeks of training ($F_{(2,44)} = 4.041 > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant reduction was accepted for changes that took place after 4weeks and rejected after 8weeks of training. Thus, longer periods of aerobic training are required to produce greater gains in %BF reduction for health and wellbeing.

Research Question 3:

Are there effects of modifications in Waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state?

Table 5: Waist and hip circumference values of subjects in the study

Variable	Before (0wk)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
d Waist cm	100cm	94cm	88cm	6.0cm (13.64%)
e. Hip cm	94cm	93.8cm	93.6cm	0.2cm

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

A cursory look at waist and hip circumferences values presented in table 3 showed that waist circumferences were 100cm at the commencement of training; and by the 4th and 8th weeks, the values changed to 94cm and 88cm; presenting a difference of 6.0cm (13.64%) and 12.0cm ((27.27%) respectively while hip circumferences were 94cm, 93.8cm and 93.6cm from the start to the end of the aerobic exercise training programme with minimal 0.2cm and 0.4cm changes at 4th and 8th weeks respectively. The result showed very minimal reduction after 8 weeks of exercise training. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was employed for analysis and the results are presented in Table 6.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₃: There are no significant effects of modifications in waist and hip circumferences on somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged female adults in Kano state

Table 6: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on waist and hip circumference

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
Waist cm	6.0cm	12.0cm	F=3.303*	3.21	NS
	(13.64%)	(27.27%)	F=4.221*		Sig
Hip cm	0.2cm	0.4cm	F=1.245	3.21	NS

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ *Significant

Examination of Table 6 revealed waist and hip circumferences of subjects in the exercise training programme. When these values were analysed with inferential statistics of One-way ANOVA, waist circumference was significant at 4weeks ($F_{(2,44)} = 3.303 > 0.05$) and 8weeks ($F_{(2,44)} = 4.221 > 0.05$) of aerobic exercise training whereas hip circumference was not. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant reduction was rejected for waist circumferences but accepted for hip circumferences. Thus,

longer period of aerobic training is expected to produce greater reductions in waist and hip circumference for health and fitness promotion.

Research Question 4

Are there changes in somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following fitness training program in Kano state?

Table 7: Data of somatotype components obtained during exercise training

Variable	Before (0wk)	During (4wks)	After (8wks)	Diff. at 4wks
Somatotype (est)	4, 4, 3 ie: 11/3=3.66	4, 4, 3 ie: 9/3=3.00	3, 3, 3: ie 9/3=3.00	No change recorded

Source: Field Assessment (2024)

Somatotype values presented in table 7 revealed values of the three components (hip, trunk and waist) as 4, 4, 3 (endomorph); 4, 4, 3 (mesomorphy) and 3, 3, 3 (ectomorphy). No changes were noticed after 4weeks of aerobic training while very minimal change was recorded at the ectomorphic level. This result revealed that exercise duration may be implicated for the minimal change recorded. In order to find out if these results are significant, the inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance was used for analysis, the results are presented in Table 8.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₄: There are no significant changes in the somatotype components of middle-aged female adults following training program in Kano state

Table 8: Results of inferential statistics of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on changes in somatotype components

Variable	Diff. after 4wks	Total changes	Fcal.	Fcrit	Remarks
Somatotype (est)	No change recorded	Very minimal	F=0.422	3.21	NS

Source: SPSS V10 data analysis (2024) $F_{(2,44)}=3.21 < 0.05$ Not Significant

A critical look at Table 8 shows the summary of somatotype response of subjects to aerobic training. The minimal changes recorded in the three aspects was not significant ($F_{(2,44)}=0.422 < 0.05$) after analysis with One way ANOVA. Each component was derived from the anthropometric formulae described by Novoa-Vignau, et al.; (2017). Therefore, this minimally insignificant value in the third component, though not significant, signifies that exercise training of long duration is more desirable for the reduction in the three components for improved health and wellness of exercise adherents.

Discussion of findings

Aerobic exercise, also known as cardio exercise, can give long-term effects to the body, especially the cardiorespiratory system consisting the heart, blood vessels and lungs. The effects can be an effective way to increase the endurance of the system when adherents maintain the exercise for a period ranging from 20 to 30 minutes, three to four times a week. The positive impact of aerobic exercise on the cardiorespiratory system includes improvements in stroke volume at rest, lower resting heart rate, lower blood pressure and consequently general well-being (Meschino, 2020). It is based on this assertion that this study compared the somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged females in their responses to 8weeks of aerobic training in Kano state.

Results on table 1a and b showed summary of physical characteristics of height and weight of subjects; in which height values, as expected, remained constant; and with 3.1% reductions in weight at the end of training. Results of data analysed with inferential statistics of One-way ANOVA to ascertain whether the 8 weeks of aerobic exercise programme has clearly and proven significant effect on variables like weight, %BF, waist circumferences of participants. Although height was not expected to change among adults after they had attained maturity, it is important in the estimation of body fat, because accumulation of excess body fat has been implicated in different ailments and degenerative diseases of among humans (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020). Considering the technicalities involved in its estimate, the field technique which used the height/weight ratio called the Quetelet Index ($\frac{wt}{ht}^2$) was applied with the Ponderal Index to obtain the body mass index (BMI) and consequently estimate the body fat percent (%BF) while, somatotype was obtained from the anthropometric technique applied by Novoa-Vignau et al.; (2017). After analysis, results showed that body weight ($F=3.312^*$), %BF ($F=4.041^*$) and

waist circumference ($F=4.221^*$) responded significantly to 8 weeks of aerobic exercise training; but the hip circumference ($F=1.245$) and somatotype ($F=0.422$) values did not, hence, were not significant. This result supports earlier works (Adeyanju & Dikko, 2015, Olaniyi, 2009) which revealed significant effect of aerobic exercise on body composition of men and women. From the results, it can be concluded that an 8-week aerobic exercise program may not lead to significant somatotype changes was also supported by Santos and Maia (2013) outcome in which they reported that the specific outcomes will depend on individual factors. This individual factor may be responsible for the significant changes in %BF (ACSM, 2018; Lee & Lee, 2015). It is recommended that participants and other exercise adherents should continue exercising, obtain appropriate nutritional guidance, and personalizing fitness plans to help them achieve and maintain their desired somatotype status while improving their overall health.

Conclusions

This study was carried out to compare the somatotype and fitness status of middle-aged adult females following an 8-week aerobic exercise programme in Kano state. The results showed significant reductions in subjects' body weight, %BF, waist circumference and slight reduction in somatotype that was not significant. The findings of this study also suggest that regular aerobic exercise can have positive impact on somatotype and fitness status in female adults. These results are consistent with previous research which support efficacy of aerobic exercise in this regard. Finally, though not significant, the slight modification of the mesomorph and ectomorph toward the end of eight weeks suggests the need for prolonged training period for maximum gains.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been put forward:

1. Women should be consistent in engaging in aerobic exercise like brisk walking, cycling and dancing in order to maintain healthy bodily characteristics, including somatotype characteristics for maximum health benefits.
2. There is need to provide exercise adherents with nutritional guidance to support their fitness goals and develop a balanced lifestyle where physical exercise plays a role.
3. Considering that responses to exercise can vary among persons, it is recommended that personalized exercise plans that better suit each participant's somatotype needs and fitness goals be encouraged.
4. Regular Assessments: Conduct periodic assessments to track physical and physiological characteristics, including somatotype status and adjust exercise and dietary recommendations accordingly. This will help participants stay on track and make necessary adjustments to achieve their desired outcomes.
5. Health Monitoring: Monitor participants' health parameters, such as blood pressure, cholesterol levels, and glucose levels, to ensure that the exercise program is contributing to overall health improvements.

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